

Development and Integration of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 FPGA Accelerator for HYP SO-1

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Abstract

The HYPerspectral imaging small Satellite for Ocean observation (HYP SO) mission uses hyperspectral images to monitor the environment by collecting images of up to hundreds of bands in the electromagnetic spectrum. This mission relies on the use of reconfigurable hardware for acceleration of onboard compression of hyperspectral images. This combats a challenge associated with small satellites as their constrained receive and transfer bandwidths and storage capabilities paired with hyperspectral images introduce limitations in their efficiency. Onboard compression is key in maximising satellite operational capacity by minimising time spent communicating and increasing the number of images that can be stored. The HYP SO-1 satellite currently uses a hyperspectral image compressor; CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standard on a Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) accelerator to compress its hyperspectral images. With the development of a near-lossless CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compliant encoder accelerator, this work has provided state-of-the-art compression speeds for implementations on smaller off-the-shelf FPGAs such as the ZYNQ-7000 series. This work describes the B-2 accelerator, the testing procedure in which upon successful RTL simulations the accelerator was tested on an on-ground HYP SO-1 system model and then passed integration tests in orbit on HYP SO-1, replacing B-1 as the defacto onboard standard in use.

CCSDS-123 compression, hyperspectral imaging, verification, testing, remote sensing, hardware accelerator, Field-Programmable Gate Array

INTRODUCTION

The HYPerspectral Small Satellite for Ocean Observation (HYP SO) is a small satellite mission developed at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) for ocean monitoring using HyperSpectral Images (HSIs). The mission currently comprises of HYP SO-1 launched in January 2022, and HYP SO-2, launched in August 2024. The HYP SO mission operates in low Earth orbit with a relatively short revisit time. Both satellites feature the same ZYNQ-7000 System on Chip (SoC), a Component Off The Shelf (COTS) processing system with Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA). This onboard processing system is part of the satellite payload and is intended for performing HSI processing including compression. Considering HSIs consist of up to hundreds of narrow colour bands distributed among two dimensions, these images allow for a more detailed analysis and understanding of the captured scene [1]. The cost however is in the size and processing requirements when dealing with images, which may be hundreds of times larger than a standard Red-Green-Blue (RGB) image. The need for compression emanates from the limited memory in the onboard COTS alongside the small satellites' constrained downlink transfer bandwidth due to the restricted antenna sizes of small satellites. The first compression method implemented for HYP SO-1 was the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) 123.0-B-1, a compression standard for lossless compression of hyperspectral images published in 2012 [2]. This was implemented in software and hardware for the HYP SO mission [3], [4]. The second issue of the standard CCSDS 123.0-B-2 [5] was published in 2019. One of the main contributions of this second issue is optional near-lossless or lossless compression modes, allowing for even higher compression ratios with a user-configurable trade-off in information loss. It also introduced a higher level of complexity, alongside backward but not forward compatibility between the standards. The issue 1 standard implementation has had significant usage aboard HYP SO-1 through a methodology of flexibility through replacement. This means that when the accelerator is being used to compress images of different widths or parameters, an accelerator pre-implemented is loaded onto the FPGA to fulfill that requirement. This has moved complexity of flexible hardware design

to software, which is more suited for this purpose. The addition of a issue 2 accelerator fits in with this methodology by providing the satellite the capability to then compress HSIs lossy or losslessly. In this manner, more images are to be stored via near-lossless format allowing for an increase in the number of images that can be transferred either in passes or kept in storage for future transfer.

BACKGROUND

The CCSDS 123 standard involves compression through two stages, a predictor stage and an encoder stage. One fixed length integer corresponding to a band of a pixel of the HSI enters the predictor known as a sample. For each sample the predictor produces a fixed length value through the difference between an adaptively weighted prediction algorithm and the actual sample value. This is then received by the encoder. The encoder outputs the compressed image. Several user configurable parameters determine the operation of the predictor and encoder defined in [5]. The main deviation from the issue 1 to issue 2 is that the issue 2 issue predictor applies quantisation steps which it uses in further processing with sample representatives rather than samples. Secondly, the hybrid entropy coder, which uses adaptive code selection to dynamically choose between high entropy and low entropy codes, is included. The high-entropy codes are equivalent to length-limited Golomb Power of 2 (GPO2) codes [6], whereas the low-entropy codes use sequences of inputs as keys to binary-output variable-length lookup tables. The quantisation introduced the lossy behaviour in the issue 2 standard and can be configured as lossless, absolute error limit or relative error limit, or both. The error limits can also be band-independent or band-dependent.

Data dependencies in CCSDS-123

CCSDS 123 compressor has several loop-carried dependencies between sample values, when considering the organisation of hyperspectral cubes. These can be categorised as two main types of dependency [7]:

- Type $z - 1$ (spectral) dependencies are where the processing of a sample $s_z(t)$ is dependent on a result from processing the same spatially located sample in the previous band $s_{z-1}(t)$.
- Type $t - 1$ (spatial) dependencies are where the processing of a sample $s_z(t)$ is dependent on a result from processing the previous sample in the same band $s_z(t - 1)$.

The ordering of samples is impacted by how data is physically represented on disk, prior pre-processing stages or any buffering strategies. Ordering alongside image dimensions affect how many samples come between spectrally consecutive and spatially consecutive samples. Resolving $t - 1$ dependencies would involve a Band Interleaved by Line (BIL) format and $z - 1$ dependencies would be Band Interleaved by Pixel (BIP) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The number of samples between consecutive type $z - 1$ and type $t - 1$ dependencies for different memory orders. Width, Height, and Bands are expressed as N_X , N_Y , and N_Z . From [7].

	BSQ	BIL	BIP
$z - 1$	$N_X N_Y$	N_X	1
$t - 1$	1	1	N_Z

Issue 2 dependencies

Figure 1 shows a dependency graph of the CCSDS 123 issue 2 predictor. Issue 2 has the eight same data dependencies as issue 1, but using sample representatives $s''_z(t)$ instead of samples $s_z(t)$ changes their significance, causing dependants to be dependent on their previous value. As a consequence, four dependencies are significant, namely $s''_z(t - 1)$ to $\sigma_z(t)$, $s''_z(t - 1)$ to $\mathbf{U}_z(t)$, $s''_{z-1}(t)$ to $\mathbf{U}_z(t)$ and $\mathbf{U}_z(t - 1)$ to $\mathbf{W}_z(t)$. The significance of three dependencies, $s_z(t)$ to $\tilde{s}_z(t)$, $\mathbf{U}_{z-1}(t)$ to $\mathbf{U}_z(t)$ and $\mathbf{W}_z(t - 1)$ to $\mathbf{W}_z(t)$ are minor. Finally, the significance of the $e_z(t - 1)$ to $\mathbf{W}_z(t)$ has increased, as the critical path from $\mathbf{W}_z(t)$ to $e_z(t)$ is longer. Issue 2 has both major type $t - 1$ and $z - 1$ dependencies, hence none of the conventional sample order approaches are sufficient to allow pipelines processing one sample per cycle at a high clock frequency.

Mathematical optimisation approach

The approach proposed by Sánchez, Blanes, Barrios [8] uses BIL ordering, applies minor limitations to configurations and mathematically optimises the remaining dependency computation. By using BIL ordering,

Figure 1: Dependency graph of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 predictor. Dependencies to previous sample results are marked with dotted edges. The most immediate dependency for each edge is illustrated. Gray-background nodes are new in issue 2.

problems related to the $z - 1$ dependency are avoided as N_X clock cycles are available. The configuration set to *narrow* local sums and *reduced prediction mode* removes the $t - 1$ dependencies that $s_z''(t)$ made significant, as it avoids using $s_z''(t - 1)$. Dependency $e_z(t - 1)$ to $\mathbf{W}_z(t)$ remains a limiting factor, but this limit is reduced by mathematically optimizing $\text{sgn}^+[e_z(t)]$ as well as using speculative execution on the calculation of $\mathbf{W}_z(t)$ for the two potential values of $\text{sgn}^+[e_z(t)]$, -1 and 1 , then selecting the correct $\mathbf{W}_z(t)$. Barrios et al. presents a predictor using this approach with a throughput of 230.5 MS/s when evaluated using High-Level Synthesis (HLS) [9].

CCSDS 123 memory usage

Memory usage is another factor that can limit CCSDS 123 FPGA implementations as high memory requirements may force the use of external memory, increasing system complexity and cost and potentially slowing down the implementation. A CCSDS 123 implementation needs to store intermediate values to be used later when compressing an image. Table 2 shows the memory requirements based on the image size and a number of configuration parameters for an issue 2 implementation. This means that compressing a nominal sized HYPISO-1 image $N_X = 956, N_Y = 684, N_Z = 120$ with $D = 16, P = 3, C_z = 6, \Omega = 19, \gamma^* = 9$ requires 1.85 Mb of memory using BIP, 1.91 Mb using BIL and 35.5 Mb using BSQ ordering, while a midrange Zynq-7030 has 9.3 Mb of BRAM [10].

Table 2: Memory requirements of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 modules using different sample ordering approaches [7].

	Sample representatives	Local differences	Weights	Accumulators
BIP	$(N_X + 1)N_Z D$	$P(D + 3)$	$N_Z C_z (\Omega + 3)$	$N_Z (D + \gamma^* + 2)$
BIL	$(N_X N_Z + 1)D$	$P N_X (D + 3)$	$N_Z C_z (\Omega + 3)$	$N_Z (D + \gamma^* + 2)$
BSQ	$(N_X + 1)D$	$P N_X N_Y (D + 3)$	$C_z (\Omega + 3)$	$D + \gamma^* + 2$

CCSDS 123 low-entropy coding challenges

The low-entropy coding in the hybrid encoder involves checking if the current active prefix matches one of the input codewords in that code. There are 16 different codes and each has between 81 and 257 codewords [6]. Their input codewords can be up to 256 input symbols $\iota_z(t)$ long. A simple approach to this problem on FPGA is to compare the active prefix to all the input codewords in that code simultaneously, but this requires a high amount of resources. The approach used by [11]–[14] is to store the codes in Trie search tree data structures and use the input symbols $\iota_z(t)$ to iteratively traverse the Trie. The codewords are organised in Read-Only

Memory (ROM) and the input symbol $\iota_z(t)$ is used to determine what address in the ROM to check. If the input symbol $\iota_z(t)$ marks the end of an input codeword, the memory contains the output codeword, if not it points toward what region of the memory to check with the next $\iota_z(t)$.

IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation approach

The implementation uses the Sánchez et al. [8] mathematical optimisation approach for reducing the throughput limiting effect of the loop-carried data dependencies. This work implements the predictor computation as a pipeline with an initiation interval of 1, with the rest of the system modules sharing this interval. The pipeline is divided into stages to the point where the indivisible weight-update stage contains the critical path limiting the maximum clock frequency.

Overview

Figure 2 shows an overview of the compressor implementation. It comprises five blocks. An optional reorder buffer inputs samples $s_z(t)$ in BIP order and outputs them in BIL order to the predictor. If samples are input to the compressor in BIL order they are input directly into the predictor. The predictor calculates and outputs mapped quantiser indexes $\delta_z(t)$ and control signals to the encoder block, which takes these inputs and generates variable length codes that are output to the packer block. In the packer block, variable length codes are split and concatenated to fit the fixed-width output bus. The controller applies control signals to the other blocks. The compressor input and output use AXI-Stream (Advanced eXtensible Interface) interfaces [15]. The predictor, encoder and packer use a global valid signal and-ed with local valid signals for handshaking. AXI-Stream valid-ready handshakes between the predictor, encoder and packer blocks is another option for this, and would avoid the large fan-out of the global valid signal but create additional complexity.

Figure 2: Top level overview of the compressor implementation.

BIP-BIL reorder buffer

The existing CCSDS 123.0-B-1 compressor on HYPSON-1 and processing infrastructure are designed to use BIP sample order, whereas this implementation involves using BIL order. To solve this without affecting the remaining HYPSON-1 system, this implementation has an optional BIP-BIL reorder buffer between the compressor input and predictor input. The BIP-BIL reorder buffer uses BRAM with the size of 2 frames, or $2N_X N_Z$ addresses. Inputs in BIP order fill the frames of the buffer column-by-column, while the outputs in BIL order read the frames of the buffer row-by-row. The buffer keeps a column counter to track how far the input is ahead of the output.

RESULTS

The supported configuration features of the final implementation are indicated in Table 3. This is also the configuration used in testing and evaluation. The hardware utilisation for the given configuration on different FPGA platforms is provided in Table 4.

Table 3: The CCSDS 123.0-B-2 configurations used for performance evaluation.

Name	Symbol	Configuration
Sample type		Unsigned
Dynamic range	D	16
Sample encoding order		BIL
Entropy coder type		Hybrid coder
Quantiser method		Absolute and relative
Number of prediction bands	P	3
Register size	R	64
Local sum type		Narrow column-oriented
Prediction mode		Reduced
Weight component resolution	Ω	19
Weight initialization method		Default
Weight update initial parameter	ν_{\min}	-1
Weight update final parameter	ν_{\max}	4
Weight update change interval	t_{inc}	2^6
Weight update exponent offsets	$\zeta_z^{(i)}, \zeta_z^*$	0
Absolute error limit	a_z	4
Relative error limit	r_z	16
Sample representative resolution	Θ	3
Sample representative offset	ψ_z	7
Sample representative damping	θ_z	3
Unary length limit	U_{\max}	18
Rescaling counter size	γ^*	6
Initial count exponent	γ_0	1
Accumulator initialization value	$\tilde{\Sigma}_z(0)$	$4 \cdot 2^{\gamma_0}$

Table 4: Resource use and performance when the compressor is implemented for HYPPO-1 images on different FPGAs.

FPGA	LUT	FF	DSP	BRAM	Power	Frequency
Zynq-7030	5242	2666	4	67.5	205 mW	66 MHz
Zynq ZU7EV	5474	2635	4	57.5	741 mW	141 MHz
Kintex XCKU040	5577	2635	4	57.5	640 mW	110 MHz

Test Procedure

In the pursuit of ensuring the correctness of the implementation, a high-level model as a golden reference is required for comparison to facilitate testing of lower abstraction levels. Prior to this work, the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 full compressor has been implemented in Python for use in the creation and verification of hardware accelerators [16]. This model provides intermediate outputs of the modules allowing for verification at each stage of the accelerator development process. In the verification procedure, compatible CCSDS test cases are run individually with the predictor and encoder modules and a small CCSDS real-world test image is simulated in RTL with the complete model. In addition, 2000 full model verification test datasets were randomly generated for random combinations of compatible compression configurations and synthetic edge cases. The verification framework including random tests and integration tests for the AXI-handshake procedure is illustrated in Figure 3. The proposed testbench allows two modes, regular and detailed mode, where in regular mode the inputs and outputs of every module are compared. In the detailed mode, every quantity defined in the standard was compared to the golden model. The test methodology uses cocotb to compare the golden model and the RTL implementation results [17]. Successfully passing these tests shows that the reorder buffer, near-lossless compression with absolute and relative limits, weight updates, sample representative calculation with parameters $\phi_z(t), \psi_z(t)$ and the hybrid encoder work according to the standard. After passing RTL testing, the configuration from Table 3 was synthesised and implemented using Vivado for testing on the ground model of HYPPO-1 with a clock frequency set to 50 Mhz. Testing was performed by providing a previously captured

nominal $956 \times 684 \times 120$ HSI, performing the compression then inspecting the result and comparing this to the result of the [18] CCSDS 123.0-B-2 implementation. Upon successful testing on the ground Onboard Processing Unit (OPU), the FPGA module was uplinked to HYPSON-1 and the compression module was tested in space on a nominal newly captured HSI alongside the currently used issue 1 accelerator for comparison.

Figure 3: Illustration of verification methodology of the Predictor, Encoder and overall system. Blue shows predictor mode where the predictor stage is simulated in RTL and interacting with the software testbench. Red is encoder mode where similarly the encoder is simulated in RTL. In system mode all modules are simulated in RTL. Detail level influences whether the intermediary computations within the predictor and encoder are analysed which is relevant during debugging.

HYPSON Mission

Compression with the implemented CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compressor was executed successfully onboard the HYPSON-1 satellite. The full details of the compared FPGA modules are in Table 5. CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compresses the 150 MB HYPSON-1 image cube to 51 MB, while the CCSDS 123.0-B-1 implementation compressed the cube to 73 MB, 43% larger than the near-lossless compressor in this test. The resulting CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compressed image is identical to the reference compressed image, produced by compressing the lossless image using the [18] implementation. The image compressed in orbit was decompressed on ground and is visualised in Figure 4.

Table 5: Resource use and performance for HYPSON-1 implementation onboard hypso-1 on nominal image.

HYPSON-1 Implementation	LUT (78600)	FF (157200)	DSP (400)	BRAM (265)	Frequency (Mhz)	Compression Test 150MB (% Reduction)	Time (ms)
Issue 1	10771 (13.7%)	8493 (5.4%)	28 (7%)	42 (15.8%)	100	73MB (51.3%)	182
Issue 2 (Reorder)	5519 (7.0%)	2867 (1.8%)	4 (1.0%)	163.5 (61.7%)	50	51MB (66%)	1449

DISCUSSION

This work has included the implementation of an optimised CCSDS 123.0-B-2 accelerator in VHDL. This model has been robustly verified in RTL against a high-level model of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 standard and passed physical tests on ground and in space. The use of a random test dataset alongside an applicable subset of the CCSDS test dataset on the predictor, encoder and as a system has been shown to provide confidence in the

Figure 4: HYPSON-1 satellite image of Railroad Valley, Nevada, USA. Compressed in space by the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compressor onboard HYPSON-1 [19].

performance of the model. The issue 2 implementation in Table 4 has shown a low resource utilisation, below that of the issue 1 implementation and lower than the state-of-the-art implementations. This is especially useful in a small satellite context where the OPU may consist of a COTS processing system with limited memory and processing resources on the smaller FPGAs. Due to the increased complexity of the issue 2 standard in the pursuit of lossy compression alongside a different optimisation method, the processing speed of the issue 2 accelerator is lower than of the issue 1 as in Table 5. The implementation of the issue 2 remains significantly faster than in software and so it has solidified its place among the tools of the mission. There is then the opportunity for the issue 2 and issue 1 to coexist in accordance with the needs of the mission, fast lossless compression used when necessary and loss-limited used as the default mode of operation. The results show a slower weight update calculation than the implementation in [9] and an alternative weight update microarchitecture using the same approach could lead to a higher throughput. The proposed implementation is flexible through reconfiguration, rather than run-time flexibility. This flexibility provides opportunities for lower resource requirements at the cost of reprogramming the FPGA. This issue 2 implementation supports a similar range of configurations as the existing issue 1 on HYPSON-1. This means that compression effectiveness can vary. While there are implementations in literature with more supported features including wide local sums, full prediction mode and band-dependent error limits, including all the quantiser fidelity control methods allows for this implementation to have higher compression ratios. However, determining optimal configurations is not the part of this work. An extension including band-dependent error limits would only incur a small increase in complexity. In terms of the configuration used in testing, this was set arbitrarily and would not cause significant error in the reconstructed image when compared to background noise.

CONCLUSION

This work proposes implementation, verification and in-space testing of a CCSDS 123.0-B-2 hyperspectral image compressor on FPGA for the HYPSON-mission satellites. It has also demonstrated the performance of a compressor implementation using the mathematical optimization data dependency approach. The compressor is capable of compressing an image on board the HYPSON-1 satellite in 1.4 seconds. HDL verification is done by comparing the implementation's simulated behavior to a golden model using various compression configurations and images. Among these is a set of 2000 randomly generated images and configurations. The compressor has successfully compressed an image in space on the HYPSON-1 satellite. To our knowledge, this is the first published mathematical dependency optimization CCSDS 123.0-B-2 approach developed in a HDL and implemented and tested in space. The throughput result of 110 MS/s on a Kintex XCKU040 FPGA shows that this reduction is not sufficient to reach the throughput of the fastest implementations in the literature. FPGA resource requirements of this implementation are the lowest among the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compressor accelerators, showing that the methodology is relevant for systems with limited FPGA resources.

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